

Report on the 2024 activities of the SeqCode Committee for the International Society for Microbial Ecology

Prepared by the SeqCode Committee Executive Board, May 28, 2025

Summary

The SeqCode Committee had a highly productive year in 2024, not only achieving several key goals but also turning challenges into opportunities for improvement and growth. Importantly, development of the SeqCode Registry continued, and more names have been added and validated. As of May 2025, a total of 808 names have been validly published under the SeqCode. An additional 228 names have been endorsed and are awaiting notification of effective publication. Following the proposal of amendments to the SeqCode in 2023, these amendments were voted on and approved by the SeqCode Community in 2024. The revised version of the SeqCode is now available on the registry website. A special issue of Systematic and Applied Microbiology on the SeqCode has been published, featuring 15 papers that illustrate growing interest and engagement from the community. During ISME19 in Cape Town, the SeqCode prize was awarded to Diego Javier Jiménez Avella, a Research Scientist at King Abdullah University of Science and Technology, Saudi Arabia, for his contributions to educational materials and use of the SeqCode in systematics. Further efforts were made to publicize the SeqCode, including posts on a dedicated BlueSky account, a roundtable discussion at ISME19 and 6 publications in peer-reviewed journals. A major challenge encountered this year was the proposal and adoption of Section 10 of the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP) by the International Committee on Systematic of Prokaryotes (ICSP). Section 10 also recognizes the importance of creating a stable nomenclature for uncultured prokaryotes, however, it includes a number of ambiguous and self-defeating provisions that will lessen its utility. The SeqCode Committee engaged in discussions with the ICSP during the evaluation of this proposal and found this to be a positive development for the SeqCode in general, indicating the willingness of ICSP to tackle the problem.

The membership of the SeqCode Committee and the Executive Board (EB) is presented in the Appendix. The Executive Board met five times in 2024, and the minutes of the meetings are included in the Appendix. The Board is deeply appreciative of the €5000 grant from ISME, which was allocated to the SeqCode Registry & Nomenclature Working Group (RNWG) for development of the Registry. The RNWG used the funds for two priority aims: curation and community engagement. For curation, €2,000 were allocated to the University of Pretoria to support the curation and registration of new names submitted to the registry. For engagement, €2,000 were allocated to establish the SeqCode Prize 2024, which included financial support to attend ISME19. The remaining €1,000 has not yet been disbursed.

SeqCode Registry & Nomenclature Working Group

The SeqCode Registry & Nomenclature Working Group (or RNWG) met three times in 2024. Under its supervision, the [SeqCode Registry](#) underwent significant advances, including implementation of a separate base code for strain number parsing and formatting called

StrainCode (ruby gem strain-code), the integration of StrainInfo API calls to import additional strain metadata and sequences, continued updates using external taxonomies (NCBI Taxonomy, GTDB, and LPSN), expanded genome modelling, introduction of abstract relationships “type material” and “reference material”, and parsing and representation of geographic sample locations.

The SeqCode Registry Curation and Editorial Team continues to function as part of the RNWG, and it currently consists of six active members and one alumnus, who review Registry submissions and semi-automated checklists. The list of members and their affiliations is available in the Appendix and at <https://registry.seqco.de/page/about>. The achievements of RNWG in 2024 include; 1) The SeqCode Registry Curation Standard Operating Procedure was expanded and is publicly available at <https://registry.seqco.de/help/curation>. 2) A Neo-Latin course was recorded with Dr. Dominik Berrens (University of Mainz), and the publication is in preparation. 3) As of May 13, 2025, a total of 808 names have been validly published under the SeqCode in 119 register lists. An additional 228 names have been endorsed by the Curation and Editorial Team and are awaiting notification of effective publication. 118 names are currently under curatorial review. 4) The NCBI LinkOut program is fully implemented, and links bring additional monthly traffic to the SeqCode Registry of about 20-25%. 5) All names validly published under the SeqCode are being registered in Wikispecies and have been assigned entries in Wikidata. This is simplified by a new implementation in the SeqCode Registry automatically producing Wiki source code. This should also simplify the pathway towards reporting all SeqCode names in Wikipedia in the future. 6) A manuscript describing the SeqCode Registry is currently in preparation.

The RNWG has identified the following priorities for 2025-2026. 1) Publication of a manuscript describing the SeqCode Registry, including computational and administrative procedures, data policies regarding FAIR principles, and community engagement. 2) Additional developments in the SeqCode Registry, will be formalized in a roadmap with specific tasks. Additional resources will be sought to support these implementation efforts.

Legislative Commission

The Legislative Commission oversees the management and consideration of proposed amendments to the SeqCode, following the processes described in Article 11 of the SeqCode statutes (Sutcliffe et al. 2024, Syst Appl Microbiol. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.syapm.2024.126498>). To date, only a single request to amend to the SeqCode has been made (Whitman et al. 2023, ISME Commun, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43705-023-00303-y>), proposing amendments to the SeqCode rules on priority of *Candidatus* names (Rule 23d) and the mechanisms for correction of typographic and orthographic errors during registration of SeqCode names (Rule 48). A public discussion on these proposals was held via the SeqCode public Slack workspace (<https://seqco.de/connect>; October 2023-January 2024) and they were put to a ballot of the SeqCode Community coordinated by Sabine van Wegen (ISME) in late May 2024. The amendments were approved in July 2024 and the results announced in October 2024 by email and notice in the SeqCode matters Zenodo site (<https://zenodo.org/communities/seqcode/>).

Subsequently, these changes were incorporated by the Legislative Commission into SeqCode version 1.1.0, which also included corrections to some minor grammatical, typographical and formatting errors. This version has been included in the SeqCode Registry and Zenodo site.

Reconciliation Committee

Amendments to the statutes passed in 2024 have already been applied in the decision about validation of the name ‘*Paceibacter normanii*’ by the **Reconciliation Committee**. Discussions about the need for further revisions to Rule 23d and the desirability of modifying Recommendation 19 to allow the designation of paratypes for cultured taxa are ongoing.

Standards Working Group

This Group has met once on zoom on Oct 03, 2023, to initiate its activities and elect Chair and co-Chair. In this first meeting, the group discussed mostly the need to change the required and recommended standards for the genome sequences of type sequences in the SeqCode taxonomic descriptions. In short, it was decided to not make any changes yet to the standards suggested by Hedlund et al., 2022, but to watch for new tools that can assess genome quality and standards more reliably than current methods as well as for new developments on the genome standards field. Examples of the latter include, but are not limited to, how new, long-read sequencing protocols could affect genome recovery from metagenomes. The group also exchanged emails about what metadata should be required or recommended to accompany the type genome sequences deposited to the INSDC databases (e.g., NCBI, ENA). Currently, the SeqCode relies on the metadata acquired by the INSDC databases for genome deposition. This discussion is ongoing and will likely be completed later in 2025.

Other developments

Efforts were made to obtain additional funding for the SeqCode. Avenues that were explored included the US National Science Foundation Research Coordination Networks program and China. Following discussions among members of the Executive Board, no proposals were submitted by the conclusion of the year.

A number of actions were undertaken to further publicize the SeqCode. Chuvochina created a new social medium channel on Bluesky, which currently has 92 followers.

Konstantinidis and Venter edited a special issue of Systematic and Applied Microbiology on the SeqCode entitled [Application of the SeqCode to name uncultivated microorganisms](#). This special issue showed the scientific community how high-quality metagenome assembled genomes (MAGs) and single amplified genomes (SAGs) can be named under the SeqCode, exemplified the needs of the scientific community working with culture-independent methods to stably name the organisms that they discover, and helped populate the list of names that will be given under this new code. It includes 13 papers published in 2024 and 2 in 2025. A particularly noteworthy paper included the valid publication of the names of *Asgardarchaeum abyssi* and the higher taxa associated with this genus.

Konstantinidis organized a workshop at the American Society for Microbiology on June 14 in Atlanta, Georgia, USA as part of the annual Microbe conference to educate attendees about the SeqCode, to answer any related questions such as differences and similarities with ICNP, and how to join the SeqCode Community. The workshop included hands-on examples on how to use the Registry system (<https://seqco.de/>) to name new prokaryotic taxa and register the corresponding type genomes. The workshop was attended by about 30-35 participants from different fields of microbiology.

Wang organized a workshop on environmental genomics including the SeqCode in Qingdao, China, in Oct, 2024. It included a training section on the SeqCode led by Rodriguez-R. The workshop included up to 50 students, provided instruction on species concepts applied to prokaryotes, diversity in prokaryotic communities, computational analysis of 16S ribosomal RNA genes, and foundational concepts in prokaryotic systematics. Participants learned the role of metagenomics and, in particular, of genome-resolved metagenomics on the characterization of prokaryotic diversity and how to analyze the quality of draft genomes recovered from metagenomes. At the conclusion of the workshop, participants were able to identify and classify genomes and recognize when taxonomic novelty was sufficient to propose new taxa, which they would be able to name under the SeqCode.

The SeqCode Committee organized a roundtable discussion at the ISME19 conference in Cape Town on 19 August 2024. Called “SeqCode - up, running and necessary”, the panel members were Luis-Miguel Rodriguez-R (AU), Marike Palmer (CAN), Stephanus Venter (RSA), Diego Javier Jiménez Avella (SA), Melandre van Lill (RSA), Maria Chuvochina (AUS) and Philip Hugenholtz (AUS).

SeqCode Committee members Chuvochina, Palmer, and Venter have joined the Senior Editorial Board of ISME Communications to establish a new taxonomy section of the journal and further promote usage of the SeqCode and its Registry.

Members of the SeqCode Committee published six papers on the SeqCode. These papers, which are listed in the Appendix, described how to use the SeqCode and provided examples of applications. In addition to providing insight into the rationale of the SeqCode, they also illustrate how the SeqCode can be widely used for valid publication of prokaryotic names. Five other papers listed in the Appendix describe either comments on the SeqCode or examples of applications.

Responding to Section 10

In 2024, the International Committee on Systematic of Prokaryotes (ICSP) discussed and eventually adopted Section 10 of the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP). Section 10 was proposed by Arahal et al. (2024) as an alternative to the SeqCode that provided formal regulations for the provisional *Candidatus* names of prokaryotes. *Candidatus* names are published names that do not meet the criteria for valid publication under the ICNP, notably the deposition of type strains in culture collections. Before Section 10, *Candidatus* names were not regulated under the ICNP. SeqCode names, where the type is a genome sequence, are, therefore, treated as *Candidatus* names under the ICNP. Section 10 created a parallel ‘pro-nomenclature’ to regulate *Candidatus* names. However, the pro-validated names only compete for priority with other *Candidatus* names and do not compete for priority with validly published names under the

ICNP, i.e. those typified by type strains. Section 10 also creates a hierarchy of types, which can be specimens, mixed cultures, as well as sequences. However, when isolates of taxa with *Candidatus* names are deposited in culture collections to serve as type strains, the *Candidatus* designation must be dropped and the species name used as the validly published name for the conspecific isolate. In this way, the system provides stable names for *Candidatus* genera and species names. However, it provides no protection for names of higher taxa. Members of the SeqCode Committee raised serious criticisms of Section 10 (Whitman and Venter, 2024). 1) It creates an unnecessary 'pro-nomenclature'. 2) It requires changes in types for *Candidatus* names. 3) It allows for changes in the category of types for *Candidatus* names. 4) It introduces requirements to 'reuse' names. 5) While it stabilizes the names of genera and species, it provides no protection for the names of higher taxa and actually encourages ignoring them. In spite of these objections, Section 10 was adopted by the ICSP with a few modifications.

A consequence of Section 10 will be the creation of ICNP names that may conflict with those of the SeqCode. The SeqCode Committee has approached the ICSP numerous times in an attempt to mitigate the consequences of creating synonyms. While the ICSP has agreed in principle to discuss the issue, they suggested postponing the discussion until 2026 and recommended forming a task group composed of members from both sides to coordinate the effort.

Appendix. Report on the activities of the SeqCode Committee for the year of 2024 for ISME

1. SeqCode Committee: administrative structure and officers as of Jan. 1, 2024
2. Minutes of the Meetings of the SeqCode Committee Executive Board
 - a. 15 February 2024.
 - b. 2 April 2024
 - c. 17 June 2024
 - d. 17 September 2024
 - e. 2 December 2024
3. Publications on the SeqCode
4. Presentations by members of the SeqCode Committee on the SeqCode

SeqCode Community Membership 2024

SeqCode Community Members

Membership in the Community is open to members of the ISME and/or others who have a demonstrable connection to microbiology (e.g., by employment or publication). It elects the SeqCode Committee and votes on proposals brought before it. Currently, it has 129 members globally.

SeqCode Committee Members

The **Executive Board** manages the constituent components of the SeqCode Committee.

Chair: William B Whitman, University of Georgia, USA; Vice-Chair: Anna-Louise Reysenbach, Portland State University, USA; Secretary: Fanus Venter, University of Pretoria, South Africa; Ex.Officio Members: Iain Sutcliffe, Northumbria University, UK; Maria Chuvochina, The University of Queensland, Australia; Luis Miguel Rodriguez-R, Universität Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria; Kostas Konstantinidis, Georgia Institute of Technology, USA; Members without Portfolio: Fengping Wang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China; Phil Hugenholtz, The University of Queensland, Australia

The **Legislative Commission** is the only body authorized to amend the SeqCode.

Chair: Iain Sutcliffe, Northumbria University, UK; Vice-Chair: Nitin Kumar Singh, NASA-JPL-Caltech, USA; Secretary: Brian Hedlund, University of Nevada, Las Vegas, USA.

The **Reconciliation Commission** is the judicial branch of the SeqCode Committee and is the only body authorized to render decisions on the application of the SeqCode.

Chair: Maria Chuvochina, The University of Queensland, Australia; Vice-Chair: Marike Palmer, University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, Canada; Secretary: Taylor Priest, Max Planck Institute for Marine Microbiology, Bremen, Germany; Additional Members: Luis Miguel Rodriguez-R, Universität Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria; Alex Probst, University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany

The **Registry & Nomenclature Working Group** maintains the SeqCode Registry

Chair: Luis Miguel Rodriguez-R, Universität Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria; Secretary:

Anwasha Ghosh, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research, Kolkata, India;

Coopted Members: Maria Dzunkova, University of Valencia, Spain; Maria Chuvochina, The University of Queensland, Australia; Marike Palmer, University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, Canada; Emiley Eloie-Fadrosch, DOE Joint Genome Institute, USA.

SeqCode Registry Curation and Editorial Team works with the **Registry & Nomenclature Working Group** and includes Marike Palmer, University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, Canada; Maria Chuvochina, The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia; Luis M Rodriguez-R., University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria; Melandre Van Lill, University of Pretoria, South Africa; Juan Valero Tebar, I2SysBio-CSIC-Universitat de València, Valencia, Spain; Emily St. John, Portland State University, Portland OR, USA.

The **Standards Working Group** monitors technical developments in the generation and quality control of sequence data and advises the SeqCode Community on recommendations for the minimum standards of genome sequences.

Chair: Kostas Konstantinidis, Georgia Institute of Technology, USA; CoChair: Cheng Li, James Madison University, USA; Coopted Members: Donovan Parks, Microba, Australia; Ramon Rossello-Mora, IMEDEA; CSIC-UIB, Mallorca, Spain; Robert Finn, European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), UK; Alice McHardy, Technical University of Braunschweig, Germany; Nikos Kyrpides, DOE Joint Genome Institute, LBNL, Berkeley, USA; Luis M Rodriguez-R., University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria.

Minutes EB24-01
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
15 February 2024 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair
Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio

Apology

Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

SeqCode Prize (to be discussed as under the item Registry and Nomenclature Working Group)

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

Action items from previous meeting

1. KK to follow-up on the NSF's' RCN and ICB funding.

Waiting for feedback on a current proposal before submitting a new proposal.

2. FW and LMR to look for Chinese funding opportunities.

FW and LMR will meet to explore the possibilities.

3. FV to remind the SeqCode Community via email of the discussion of the proposal to amend the SeqCode, and the SeqCode prize. The help of volunteer nomenclature curators will also be requested.

Done, but no response yet for assistance with curation.

4. PH to investigate the possibility of continued funding from ISME for work on the registry.

PH to provide feedback.

5. LMR and MC to look into the possible incorporation of GAN in the registry.

GAN could be incorporated. Program will assist with the creation of names and could reduce the workload of the curators. Could not be used as a check for names proposed by authors.

6. MC to prepare a proposal for a roundtable discussion at ISME19.

FW suggested a candidate for the community panel. Proposal to be submitted on 16 February.

7. Redacted

8. EB to prepare a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode for submission to ISME communications after January 2024.

BW to manage processes and submit final report to ISME Executive. IS, LMR, KK and MC to provide a short summary of their activities by March 1.

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

The public discussion of the Whitman et al. proposal to amend the SeqCode is completed and IS has provided the necessary documentation required for the ballot. FV and LMR to liaise with the ISME office to prepare the ballot via surveymonkey. Voting will be open for 1 month. FV to alert the SeqCode Community of the opportunity to vote. Results will be compiled and shared by FV and LMR.

Standards Working Group

No new issues to report.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 221 names have been validated and another 229 have been endorsed.

LMR expressed the concern that the current curation team is working at capacity. LMR hopes that Melandre van Lill could continue as part of the curation team to assist with the curation of names with Marike Palmer as mentor. Juan Valero (from the group of Maria Dzunkova, Universidad de Valencia) and Emily St John (from ALR lab) will join the team to assist with checking the genome quality requirements.

The activities of the SeqCode will be promoted at the IMMSA Webinar and the NMDC Champions program.

MC and LMR will investigate the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.

The Neo-Latin department of the University of Innsbruck has expressed interest in joining a possible EU COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology) action.

Three submissions were received for the SeqCode Prize. The entries will be shared with the EB and members who do not have an association with one or more of the applicants will evaluate the entries and make the final decision.

Reconciliation Commission

The discussion of the proposal for validation of a name linked to a poor-quality genome to ensure the stability of the names of the higher-ranking taxa has been completed and the documentation was shared with the SeqCode Community. There is now a 3-month period for objections to be raised. If no objections are received by 12 March 2024 the decision will be ratified.

5. Discussion of Arahal et al. proposed amendments to the ICNP

EB members will provide their comments for discussion at the next EB meeting. Comments should only focus on the proposed amendments to the ICNP and their implications. Individuals are welcome to provide comments on the proposal via the ICSP Slack channel.

6. Conference and Meeting Updates

EB members are encouraged to list SeqCode presentations and share material linked to these presentations on the shared drive.

New action items

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
2. BW to manage the compilation a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode and submit it to the ISME Executive. Publication in ISME Communications to be investigated.
3. IS, LMR, KK and MC to provide a short summary of their activities for the SeqCode report by 1 March 2023.
4. FV and LMR to liaise with the ISME office to prepare the ballot for the proposed changes to the SeqCode.
5. FV to alert the SeqCode Community of the opportunity to vote.
6. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot and share it with the EB.
7. MC and LMR to investigate the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.
8. FV to share the SeqCode prize entries with EB members to evaluate the entries and make the final decision.
9. EB members to provide their comments on the Arahall et al. proposal for discussion at the next EB meeting.
10. MC to contact a candidate for community panel proposed by FW and submit the roundtable proposal for ISME19.
11. All to reflect and suggest on more involvement of ISME with SeqCode.

Ongoing action items

1. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.
2. FW and LMR to look for Chinese funding opportunities.
3. PH to investigate the possibility of continued funding from ISME for work on the registry.

Minutes prepared by FV, 18 February 2024

Approved 27 February 2024

Minutes EB24-02
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
8 April 2024 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair
Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio

Apology

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Session at the ASM meeting.

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

Action items from previous meeting

1. KK to follow-up on the NSF's RCN and ICB funding.

Will follow-up on this matter in May

2. FW and LMR to look for Chinese funding opportunities.

A workshop similar to what was proposed for ISME will be presented in October in China. The assistance of a post-doc from the group of FW will also be investigated.

3. PH to investigate the possibility of continued funding from ISME for work on the registry.

PH will confirm with Linda Scholten (ISME Executive Director) but understanding is that funding for 2024 will be at the same levels as in 2023.

4. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.

Done

5. BW to manage the compilation a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode and submit it to the ISME Executive. Publication in ISME Communications to be investigated.

BW is still waiting for summary reports

6. IS, LMR, KK and MC to provide a short summary of their activities for the SeqCode report by 1 March 2023.

IS provided report. LMR, KK and MC to provide report by 30 April.

7. FV and LMR to liaise with the ISME office to prepare the ballot for the proposed changes to the SeqCode.

Voting is delayed due to the workload of the ISME office. An alternative will be discussed.

8. FV to alert the SeqCode Community of the opportunity to vote.

Ongoing

9. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot and share it with the EB.

Ongoing

10. MC and LMR to investigate the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.

Some entries are already linked to the SeqCode. This was possibly done by the authors who submitted the genomes. LMR to make a formal request via PubMed LinkOut.

11. FV to share the SeqCode prize entries with EB members to evaluate the entries and make the final decision.

Community was informed that Dr Diego Jimenez from KAUST, Saudi Arabia won the prize.

12. EB members to provide their comments on the Arahall et al. proposal for discussion at the next EB meeting.

Response discussed during the meeting. See below

13. MC to contact a candidate for community panel proposed by FW and submit the roundtable proposal for ISME19.

Done. Currently waiting for the outcome of the application.

14. Redacted

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

Waiting for the assistance from the ISME office to launch ballot on amending SeqCode. If they cannot assist by the end of April due to their involvement in organising ISME19, FV will send out the ballots directly via email. Voting will be open for 1 month. Results will be compiled and shared by FV and LMR.

Standards Working Group

No new issues to report.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 268 names have been validated and another 249 have been endorsed.

Several people have joined the curation team. The eighth member to join is Prof Giovanna Felis, University of Verona, Italy who will assist with the nomenclature reviews. LMR and BW to discuss some formal acknowledgement for the efforts of the curation team.

The Neo-Latin department of the University of Innsbruck has expressed interest in creating an online session to expose the systematic community to the basic principles of naming using Latin. LMR and FV will discuss the possibility to present this as a BISMIS Live workshop with Kamlesh Jangid.

Reconciliation Commission

The issue of how to validate the name of a genus as part of a later publication was discussed. The EB decided to recommend the optional inclusion of the original (not valid) publication in the formal name citation, and the listing of that publication in the SeqCode Registry entry. The recommended citation should be in parenthesis before the valid publication reference, and preceded by the "ex" particle. These recommendations refer only to the citation of names after valid publication. These changes are to be implemented in the SeqCode Registry as soon as possible.

5. Discussion of Arahal et al. proposed amendments to the ICNP

BW prepared a document outlining the concerns related to the Arahal et al. proposal. The EB supported the views expressed and discussed how this information should be shared with the wider community. After finalising the document BW will post these comments on the ICSP Slack channel. BW will also circulate it among members of the SeqCode Committee and provide a Google sheet that people could use to indicate that they are willing to support this document as signatories. This data could also be shared with the wider community (e.g original webinar attendees)

6. Conference and Meeting Updates

KK has shared the description for the function at ASM Microbe 2024, Atlanta, USA on Friday 14 June.

EB members are encouraged to list SeqCode presentations and share material linked to these presentations on the shared drive.

New action items

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
2. LMR to make a formal request via PubMed LinkOut for SeqCode validated names to be linked with the registry.
3. LMR and BW to discuss some formal acknowledgement for the efforts of the curation team.
4. LMR and FV to contact Kamlesh Jangid to enquire if the proposed session by the Neo-Latin department could be accommodated on BISMis Live.
5. KK to submit the description of the proposed SeqCode function at ASM Microbe 2024.
6. BW will post the comments on the Arahal et al. proposal on the ICSP Slack channel.
7. BW to circulate the comments on the Arahal et al. proposal among members of the SeqCode Committee and provide a Google sheet that people could use to indicate that they are willing to support this document as signatories.

Ongoing action items

1. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.
2. PH to confirm the SeqCode funding from ISME for 2024 with Linda Scholten.
3. BW to manage the compilation a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode and submit it to the ISME Executive. Publication in ISME Communications to be investigated.
4. LMR, KK and MC to provide a short summary of their activities for the SeqCode report by 30 April 2024
5. FV and LMR to liaise with the ISME office to prepare the ballot for the proposed changes to the SeqCode.
6. FV to alert the SeqCode Community of the opportunity to vote for the amendment of the SeqCode.
7. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot and share it with the EB.

Minutes prepared by FV: 9 April 2024

Approved: 24 April 2024

Minutes EB24-03
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
17 June 2024 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Apology

Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Session at the ASM meeting.

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

Action items from previous meeting

Ongoing action items

1. KK to follow-up on the NSF RCN and ICB funding

To follow-up.

2. PH to investigate the possibility of continued funding from ISME for work on the registry.

Decision is linked to the submission of the report to ISME.

LMR will administer current and future funds via an account at the University of Innsbruck.

3. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.

Completed.

4. BW to manage the compilation a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode and submit it to the ISME Executive. Publication in ISME Communications to be investigated.

Report to be finalised asap. Currently awaiting comments from MC. FV to submit it to Linda Scholten at ISME.

5. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot for the proposed changes to the SeqCode.

Ballot currently open until the end of June. A response rate of 33% is required. FV to contact Sabine van Wegen to ask for a reminder to be sent to Community members. Ensure that all voting members received the ballot as the original email from SurveyMonkey went to the spam folder for some of the members.

6. MC and LMR to investigate the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.

Linkout application was submitted but no response yet.

7. BW and FV to share comments on the Arahal et al. proposal published in special issue of SAM.

Commentary published in Systematic and Applied Microbiology

(<https://authors.elsevier.com/c/1jGEp2aR~NISK5>)

8. FV, LMR and MC to discuss BISMIS live discussions on Arahal et al. proposal

BW, LMR and MC presented at BISMIS Live on 18 May.

(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1ot1DR65Tbg>).

9. MC to contact a candidate for community panel proposed by FW and submit the roundtable proposal for ISME19.

The list of people to participate in the ISME Roundtable discussion has been finalized. MC shared an outline of possible topics for discussion. The discussion should focus on the success of the SeqCode and how its operation could be improved. Feedback to MC from EB members by 8 July.

10. All to reflect and suggest on more involvement of ISME with SeqCode

Redacted

FV to contact the ISME Ambassador Program's Director, Thulani Makhalenyane to discuss the possibility on demonstrating the use of the SeqCode Registry at regional ISME meetings. MLR with the assistance of Emily St John will start with the preparation of materials that can be used and shared.

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

The ballot dealing with changes to the SeqCode has been launched and is open until the end of June. A response rate of 33% is required.

An email discussion on the advantages of including the use of an isolate as a paratype in the SeqCode will be continued on RocketChat. A paratype is defined as a specimen of an organism that helps define what the scientific name of a species and other taxon actually represents, but it is not the holotype. Minor alterations to Recommendation 19 and SeqCode section 6 would be needed to introduce this.

Standards Working Group

No new issues to report. KK will contact Emily Eloë-Fadrosh to see how the SeqCode could benefit from the current discussions related to STORMS (Strengthening the organization and reporting of microbiome studies).

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 503 names have been validated and another 83 are under review.

Prof Beata Gaj from the Department of Greek and Latin Literature at the Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University in Warsaw, Poland has joined the curation team to provide guidance on Latin naming when required.

A slide with the photos of the Curation team is available for use in presentations. Redacted

The SeqCode usage will be legally monitored using Plausible.

Redacted

Reconciliation Commission

The commission will start to address the issue of names listed in the registry that should not be treated as validly published as their type genomes do not meet the current quality requirements or they have been validated with an incorrect effective publication (e.g., taxon names proposed based on 16S rRNA genes and later described in a publication with a genome representative).

5. Discussion of Arahal et al. proposed amendments to the ICNP

BW and FV published a commentary outlining the concerns related to the Arahal et al. proposal in Systematic and Applied Microbiology. This commentary was supported by around 80 additional microbiologists from across the globe. The 34th BISMIS Live session on 18 May where BW, LMR and MC presented their views on the matter will now be followed by a presentation by ICSP members on 22 June. These sessions are recorded and will be available on the BISMIS Live YouTube channel. The session from 18 May has already been viewed 404 times, making it among the most viewed sessions on this channel.

6. DSI membership

MC will find out how the SeqCode could become a member of the DSI network.

7. EB discussion to move to Rocket Chat

The EB discussion will now formally move to RocketChat. Redacted

8. SeqCode presence on social media

It was decided that we will continue using our profile on X to promote activities of the SeqCode.

9. Conference and Meeting Updates

KK reported that the function at ASM Microbe 2024, Atlanta, was attended by around 30 people who showed interest in how to use the SeqCode.

LMR uploaded the presentation he gave at the University of Aalborg in May on the registry. Redacted

New action items

- 1.** FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
- 2.** FV to contact Sabine van Wegen to ask for a reminder to be sent to Community members on the vote for the SeqCode amendments.
- 3.** All EB members to provide feedback on the ISME roundtable discussion document to MC by 8 July.
- 4.** FV to contact Thulani Makhalenyane to discuss the promotion of the SeqCode at regional ISME meetings. Offer the possibility of virtual tutorials on how to use the Registry.
- 5.** MLR with the assistance of Emily St John to start with the preparation of materials to demonstrate the use of the SeqCode registry at meetings.
- 6.** MC enquire about the SeqCode becoming a member of the DSI network.
- 7.** All EB members to familiarise themselves with RocketChat and to contribute to the discussion thread on the use of an isolate as a paratype in the SeqCode.

Ongoing action items

1. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.
2. PH to confirm the SeqCode funding from ISME for 2024 with Linda Scholten after the formal report has been submitted.
3. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot to amend the SeqCode and share it with the EB.
4. LMR to follow-up on the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.

Minutes prepared by FV: 17 June 2024

Approved: 21 June 2024

Minutes EB24-03
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
17 September 2024 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK-)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Apology

Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio

1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

None.

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

- 1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.*
Completed.
- 2. FV to contact Sabine van Wegen to ask for a reminder to be sent to Community members on the vote for the SeqCode amendments.*
Completed.
- 3. All EB members to provide feedback on the ISME round table discussion document to MC by 8 July.*
Completed, see feedback of ISME round table under specific agenda item.
- 4. FV to contact Thulani Makhalenyane to discuss the promotion of the SeqCode at regional ISME meetings. Offer the possibility of virtual tutorials on how to use the Registry.*
Suggestion was that FV will contact the various ISME ambassadors to offer our assistance in supporting or presenting a SeqCode session at any of the regional conferences.
- 5. LMR with the assistance of Emily St John to start with the preparation of materials to demonstrate the use of the SeqCode registry at meetings.*
LMR busy preparing material which will first be used at the Chinese Microbial Ecology meeting in October. The Department of Neo-Latin at the University of Innsbruck is assisting with a video to explain the creation of acceptable Latin taxon names. This will be launched during a BISMIS Live event in 2025.
- 6. MC enquire about the SeqCode becoming a member of the DSI network.*
The DSI Network membership is only available for individuals. MC has registered and will inform the EB of any relevant information shared with her.

7. All EB members to familiarise themselves with RocketChat and to contribute to the discussion thread on the use of an isolate as a paratype in the SeqCode.

The discussion on paratypes will continue on RocketChat.

8. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.

KK will report when he has additional information.

9. PH to confirm the SeqCode funding from ISME for 2024 with Linda Scholten after the formal report has been submitted.

Linda Scholten has informed the EB that funding for the SeqCode will now be processed according to the general ISME policy. The current funding will be for 2023 and 2024. An application for funding for 2025 needs to be submitted to ISME early in 2025. Payment for 2024 will only be processed once a short final report, which will be posted on the ISME website, has been submitted. LMR will finalize the 2024 funding report and forward it to BW and FV to be submitted to the ISME office.

10. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot to amend the SeqCode and share it with the EB.

The results have been compiled. Of the 64 members who participated, 55 supported the amendments, 2 rejected the amendments and 7 opted to abstain.

11. LMR to follow-up on the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.

The SeqCode registry is now linked.

12. All to reflect and suggest on more involvement of ISME with SeqCode.

Redacted

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

The ballot dealing with changes to the SeqCode has been finalized. The outcome will be shared with the SeqCode Community (as above). It was decided that no formal publication will be necessary. IS will update and Version 1.1.0 of the SeqCode will now be posted on the Registry and ISME websites, as per the Statutes.

Standards Working Group

No new issues to report. The working group was asked to discuss the possibility of providing minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries. The current policy dealing with metadata is already explained as part of the FAQ on the Registry website.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 585 names have been validated and another 249 have been endorsed. These names have been published in around 30 different journals which is indicative of uptake by the larger microbiology community. It is suggested that a report on the success of the Registry be published as part of the mid-term and final report of the current EB.

The working group is finalizing an internal policy on how to deal with incomplete entries. It was agreed that authors will be asked to respond within a month after being contacted. Afterwards no guarantee can be given that names will still be protected.

Reconciliation Commission

The commission will have a meeting in the near future to discuss any possible issues.

5. Discussion of Arahal et al. proposed amendments to the ICNP

FV reported that after a number of minor changes, voting on the proposed changes to the ICNP has been initiated and would be completed by 4 December. In the case that the proposed rules are accepted, SeqCode names can be pre-validated by submission for inclusion on Candidatus lists. We should alert the community that for this to happen, the etymology and protologue should be published as part of the main text of the paper and not Supplementary Material.

6. Report on ISME roundtable

The roundtable held during the ISME 19 conference in Cape Town was well attended. Various issues were discussed such as the quality of genomes, replacement of type genomes in case of the availability of a better-quality genome and AI tools to assist with the creation of Latin names for taxa. The audience expressed their appreciation for the work done by the various SeqCode committees and working groups.

It was suggested that the EB initiates a discussion to develop guidelines for the consultation process with First Peoples when taxon names linked to their culture or language are proposed. It was suggested to ask Marike Palmer and Casey Hubert from Canada to assist the EB.

7. EB discussion to move to Rocket Chat

The policy related to the use of RocketChat has changed and there is a restriction on the number of people who can participate on the free version. The EB decided that the SeqCode Community discussion will remain on Slack.

8. SeqCode presence on social media

FV will investigate the creation of a profile for the SeqCode on LinkedIn. The creation of a Wikipedia page will also be investigated.

9. Conference and Meeting Updates

LMR will upload the ISME poster dealing with the Registry on the drive. FV will also upload a paper on the "Options and considerations for validation of prokaryotic names under the SeqCode" which was accepted for publication in the SeqCode special issue of Systematic and Applied Microbiology.

Redacted

New action items

- 1.** FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
- 2.** FV to circulate the outcome of the ballot on changes to the SeqCode and have it posted on the ISME and Registry websites.
- 3.** FV to contact the various ISME ambassadors to offer our assistance in supporting or presenting a SeqCode session at any of the regional conferences.
- 4.** LMR to finalize the 2024 report on ISME funding and forward it to BW and FV to be submitted to the ISME office.
- 5.** The EB to prepare a request for ISME funding in 2025 and submit it early in the new year.

6. IS to prepare SeqCode Version 1.1.0 and organise its posting on the Registry and ISME websites.
7. KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.
8. FV to investigate the creation of a profile for the SeqCode on LinkedIn.
9. FV to investigate the creation of a Wikipedia page for the SeqCode
10. BW to contact Marike Palmer to ask her to lead a discussion to develop guidelines for the consultation process with First Peoples when taxon names linked to their culture or language are proposed.

Ongoing action items

1. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.
2. EB members to participate in the discussion on paratypes on RocketChat.

Minutes prepared by FV: 20 September 2024

Approved: 28 September 2024

Minutes EB24-04
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
2 December 2024 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair
Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio

1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Interactions with ISME Communications - PH

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

- 1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.*
Completed
- 2. FV to circulate the outcome of the ballot on changes to the SeqCode and have it posted on the ISME and Registry websites.*
Completed
- 3. FV to contact the various ISME ambassadors to offer our assistance in supporting or presenting a SeqCode session at any of the regional conferences.*
Ongoing. FV to interact with Kelly Wrighton, the new Director of the ISME Ambassador Program.
- 4. LMR to finalize the 2024 report on ISME funding and forward it to BW and FV to be submitted to the ISME office.*
LMR submitted a report to claim part of the expenses.
- 5. The EB to prepare a request for ISME funding in 2025 and submit it early in the new year.*
LMR expressed concern related to the ISME requirement that funding could not be used for the payment of persons assisting with the development of the Registry. PH will request the ISME Board to reconsider this requirement.
- 6. IS to prepare SeqCode Version 1.1.0 and organise its posting on the Registry and ISME websites.*
Ongoing. IS will add a note indicating that this version is an update and reflects all changes in the SeqCode to date. LMR will provide IS with Version 1.03, which corrected some small errors, so IS can ensure that these were incorporated into Version 1.1.0. IS will share the final version with MC, FV and LMR to post on the various platforms.
- 7. KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.*

KK asked for clarification on what the intention of this recommendation should be, as well as where the metadata should be stored. It was agreed that the metadata should be directly linked to the genome data and should not be captured as part of the Registry.

8. FV to investigate the creation of a profile for the SeqCode on LinkedIn.

FV has created a SeqCode group linked to his profile. LMR will supply images of the SeqCode logo to be used as a banner for the group's contact page.

9. FV to investigate the creation of a Wikipedia page for the SeqCode.

Wikipedia discourages the creation of an article by a person with a connection to the topic. It was decided that the EB will proceed with the creation of a page, but that our relationship with the SeqCode will be disclosed. FV to draft a text and circulated it amongst the EB.

10. BW to contact Marike Palmer to ask her to lead a discussion to develop guidelines for the consultation process with First Peoples when taxon names linked to their culture or language are proposed.

Completed. Marike Palmer agreed to lead this discussion.

11. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.

Ongoing.

12. EB members to participate in the discussion on paratypes on RocketChat.

BW to prepare a draft proposal for possible amendments to the code for further discussion by the EB.

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

Version 1.1.0 of the SeqCode will be posted on the Registry and ISME websites, as per the Statutes.

Standards Working Group

The working group will still discuss the possibility of providing minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 646 names have been validated and another 247 have been endorsed.

Reconciliation Commission

The commission will soon have a meeting to discuss any possible issues.

5. Discussion of Arahal et al. proposed amendments to the ICNP

FV reported that it was reported at the ICSP meeting in Florence that the proposed rules will be accepted; the formal announcement is expected shortly after 4/12/24. We are now waiting to see how these new rules will be implemented. There is uncertainty whether names in the SeqCode linked to genomes obtained from isolates will be pro-validated. The registry will alert users that SeqCode names could possibly be pre-validated in cases where the etymology and protologue were published as part of the main text of the paper and not in the Supplementary Material.

6. Dialog between the ICSP, BISMis and the SeqCode

The Bergey's Manual Trust invited the SeqCode EB to participate in constructive discussions on how potential issues that could arise from the use of both the SeqCode and the ICNP could be resolved. After

some debate it was decided that the SeqCode EB will participate in such a discussion should the other parties also agree to this dialogue. FV to inform the Bergey's Manual Trust of our decision.

7. SeqCode presence on social media

MC will create a profile for the SeqCode on Bluesky and will investigate the use of a starter pack.

8. Conference and Meeting Updates

EB members are encouraged to submit any relevant documents on the shared drive.

Redacted

9. Interactions with ISME Communications

PH will contact Hauke Smidt to initiate discussions between Hauke and FV to establish a special category for species descriptions in ISME communications. The recent paper by Dutkiewicz et al (2024) in the journal serves as an excellent example of the type of paper that could be included in such a section.

10. AOB

IS reminded the EB that the statutes require the Chairs of the Commissions and Working Groups to provide mid-term reports in early 2025.

New action items

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
2. FV to interact with Kelly Wrighton to offer our assistance in supporting or presenting a SeqCode session at any of the regional conferences.
3. PH to request the ISME Board to reconsider the requirement that ISME funding cannot be used for the payment of persons assisting with the development of the Registry.
4. IS to add a note indicating that this version is an update and reflects all changes in the SeqCode to date.
5. LMR to provide IS with Version 1.03, which corrected some small errors, so IS can ensure that these were incorporated into Version 1.1.0.
6. IS to share the revised version of the Code with MC, FV and LMR for posting on the various platforms.
7. LMR to supply images of the SeqCode logo to be used as a banner for the group's LinkedIn contact page.
8. FV to draft a text for a Wikipedia article on the SeqCode and circulated it amongst the EB.
9. BW to prepare a draft proposal for possible amendments to the code to include paratypes for further discussion by the EB.
10. FV to inform the Bergey's Manual Trust of our decision to participate in the proposed dialogue.
11. MC to create a profile for the SeqCode on Bluesky and to investigate the use of a starter pack.
12. PH to contact Hauke Smidt to initiate discussions between Hauke and FV to establish a special category for species descriptions in ISME communications.

13. KK, IS, MC and LMR to prepare interim reports from the commissions or working groups to be tabled at the next EB meeting.

Ongoing action items

1. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.
2. KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.

Minutes prepared by FV: 3 December 2024

Approved: 9 December 2024

Publications on the SeqCode

Publications by members of the SeqCode Committee

- DUTKIEWICZ, Z., SINGLETON, C. M., SEREIKA, M., VILLADA, J. C., MUSSIG, A. J., CHUVOCHINA, M., ALBERTSEN, M., SCHULZ, F., WOYKE, T., NIELSEN, P. H., HUGENHOLTZ, P. & RINKE, C. 2025. Proposal of *Patescibacterium danicum* gen. nov., sp. nov. in the ubiquitous bacterial phylum Patescibacteriota phyl. nov. *ISME Commun*, 5, ycae147.
- SUTCLIFFE, I. C., RODRIGUEZ, R. L., VENTER, S. N. & WHITMAN, W. B. 2024. Quis custodiet ipsos custodes? A call for community participation in the governance of the SeqCode. *Syst Appl Microbiol*, 47, 126498.
- VAN LILL, M., VENTER, S. N., MUEMA, E. K., PALMER, M., CHAN, W. Y., BEUKES, C. W. & STEENKAMP, E. T. 2024. SeqCode facilitates naming of South African rhizobia left in limbo. *Syst Appl Microbiol*, 47, 126504.
- VENTER, S. N., RODRIGUEZ, R. L., CHUVOCHINA, M., PALMER, M., HUGENHOLTZ, P. & STEENKAMP, E. T. 2024. Options and considerations for validation of prokaryotic names under the SeqCode. *Syst Appl Microbiol*, 47, 126554.
- WHITMAN, W. B., CHUVOCHINA, M., HEDLUND, B. P., KONSTANTINIDIS, K. T., PALMER, M., RODRIGUEZ, R. L., SUTCLIFFE, I. & WANG, F. 2024. Why and how to use the SeqCode. *mLife*, 3, 1-13.
- WHITMAN, W. B. & VENTER, S. N. 2024. Commentary on the proposed Section 10 amendments to the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes regarding Candidatus names. *Syst Appl Microbiol*, 47, 126524.

Publications by others

- ARAHAL, D., BISGAARD, M., CHRISTENSEN, H., CLERMONT, D., DIJKSHOORN, L., DUIM, B., EMLER, S., FIGGE, M., GOKER, M., MOORE, E. R. B., NEMEC, A., NORSKOV-LAURITSEN, N., NUBEL, U., ON, S. L. W., VANDAMME, P. & VENTOSA, A. 2024. The best of both worlds: a proposal for further integration of Candidatus names into the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol*, 74.
- AZNAR, R., MISTOU, M. Y., RAHI, P., LEGRAS, J. L., BORODUSKE, A., STEFANIU, A., LIMA, N., KARAGOUNI, A. D., VAN DE PERRE, V. & MELO, A. M. P. 2025. MIRRI-ERIC's position on the recent evolution of the international code of nomenclature of prokaryotes. *Syst Appl Microbiol*, 48, 126587.
- GAGO, J. F., VIVER, T., URDIAIN, M., FERREIRA, E., ROBLEDO, P. & ROSSELLO-MORA, R. 2024. Metagenomics of two aquifers with thermal anomalies in Mallorca Island, and proposal of new uncultivated taxa named following the rules of SeqCode. *Syst Appl Microbiol*, 47, 126506.

JIMENEZ, D. J. & ROSADO, A. S. 2024. SeqCode in the golden age of prokaryotic systematics. *ISME J*, 18.

PLUM-JENSEN, L. E., SCHRAMM, A. & MARSHALL, I. P. G. 2024. First single-strain enrichments of *Electrothrix* cable bacteria, description of *E. aestuarii* sp. nov. and *E. rattekaaiensis* sp. nov., and proposal of a cable bacteria taxonomy following the rules of the SeqCode. *Syst Appl Microbiol*, 47, 126487.

Presentations on the SeqCode by the SeqCode Committee

Chuvochina M. 2025. SeqCode: from idea to implementation. In Spring Symposium: DNA sequences as types, 7 April. Utrecht, Netherlands,

Konstantinidis K. 2024. Invited speaker, annual meeting of the Society for Applied Microbiology, VAAM. Würzburg, Germany. June 4th, 2024.

Konstantinidis K. 2024. Invited speaker, the annual meeting of the American Society for Microbiology, Microbe. Atlanta, GA, USA. June 14th, 2024.

Konstantinidis K. 2024. Invited lecturer, Emory University, Department of Biology, seminar series. Atlanta, GA, USA. September 20th, 2024.

Konstantinidis K. 2024. Invited speaker, Taxon XX congress of the Spanish Society for Prokaryotic Taxonomy. Salamanca, Spain. September 27th, 2024.

Konstantinidis K. 2024. Invited speaker, the microbial ecology congress of the Chinese society for Microbial Ecology. Qingdao, China. October 27, 2024.

Rodriguez-R, LM. October 2024. The SeqCode provides a stable nomenclature including the uncultivated: why do we need it and how do we use it? In: International Seabed Authority Fellowship Program, Shanghai, China.

Rodriguez-R, LM; Rossello-Mora, R; Viver, T; Ernster, N. October 2024. Environmental genomics and the SeqCode. In: General Meeting of the Chinese Association of Microbial Ecology (CAME), Qingdao, China.

Rodriguez-R, LM. April 2024. Using genomes on the ststenatucs of *Archaea* and *Bacteria* and why we need the SeqCode. In: A view of prokaryotic taxonomy on the basis of genomic and metagenomic data, Bogotá, Colombia.

Whitman, WB; Rodriguez-R, LM; Chuvochina, M. May 2024. Amendments to introduce *Candidatus* into the code is not the best of both worlds. In: The Bergey's International Society for Microbial Systematics (BISMiS) Live, Online.

Whitman WB. 2024. Two codes of prokaryotic nomenclature: how do they become one? 8th International Conference of Indian Network for Soil Contamination Research (INSCR), Plenary online presentation.